

NEW INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES.

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Annotation: *The article analyzes the ways of developing students' linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic and strategic competences within the framework of communicative approach in learning English with the help of innovative technologies, the methodical support of using innovative technologies based on the development of independent education.*

Keywords: *linguistics, pragmatic and strategic competences, English language, innovative, technology, educational technologies, interactive, method.*

In today's educational institutions, using modern pedagogical technologies, there are ample opportunities for learning foreign languages and preparing specialists who can speak these languages fluently.

In the world, the adoption of international standards in learning foreign languages, modernization of learning content, special issues of the use of modern technologies in professional education, and the development of professional competencies of the learner have strengthened the desire to use advanced foreign experiences. Foreign languages in Europe

In this regard, it is important to carry out scientific research on the development of professional competencies, integration of competencies, formation of compatibility between standard requirements and study programs, coordination of developed criteria and strategies used in learning other foreign languages.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In our country, J. Jalolov, G. Bokieva, T. Sattorov, G. T. Makhkamova, L. A. Akhmedova, U. Khoshimov, I. Yakubov, S. Musinov, L. Kirkham, M. T. Iriskulov,

F. Rashidova In his studies, the problems related to the methodology of learning foreign languages are covered in detail.

RESULTS

According to the information of the National Training Center of the United States of America, innovative technology, that is, an interactive method, affects the student's mind, feelings, will, and improves his thinking. In practice, methodist-sleepers used "Brainstorming", "Basic Signals", "Muz Yarak", "Working in a small group", "Zigzag", "Cubic", "On a deserted island", "Wise talk", "Written discussions", " It became known that they use interactive methods such as "Jigsaw", "6x6x6", "Rolly houses", "Bakhs discussion", "Debates", "Adventure journey". Student activity in interactive education consists of the following:

K, increase the friction

To control the concepts

Knowing the motive

- Increase activity and exchange of information

- Independent learning and

independence

- To work with sources

Student activity in interactive learning

The state of development of linguistic competencies of future foreign language learners requires the analysis of language learning and language acquisition, linguistic competences of learners, as well as the traditional learning system and modern learning technologies. The formation and development of students' linguistic competence in English language classes is closely related to the ability to choose the methods and methods of education, and it is necessary to increase the interest in learning foreign languages and organize independent education in language learning.

DISCUSSION

Brain storming method. This method shows the active participation of students and the level of their knowledge. This encourages students to come up with ideas, allows them to freely communicate and, as a result, generate more ideas. The sleeper is considered the supervisor during the process. Although the students' ideas are not very successful, the listener cannot criticize them. On the contrary, it is necessary to encourage creative thinking of students. The lesson ends with encouraging quick answers, filling them in, and evaluating students.

The method of questions and answers and picture houses (Discussion) makes the lessons more meaningful and interesting. A student should be able to express his opinion freely without being afraid of making mistakes. Such an atmosphere should be created in the lesson. The tasks of the student in the technology of home automation are as follows:

1. Anticipate responses and objections.
2. Belief in one's own knowledge.

The importance of the game is that the listener has the opportunity to observe the students while they are freely active. As a result, it is possible to get detailed information about students' activity, imagination, creative abilities, diligence, behavior in the team. Students are divided into several groups. Each member of the group should know their duties clearly. The time of the game should be limited, and after its completion, the results of the game should be analyzed. Home-based learning technologies also create a wide range of opportunities for students to gain deep knowledge in the educational process. One of the main goals of modern pedagogical technologies is to make students interested in English language teaching and achieve continuous improvement of knowledge.

Another method of learning English is the modern interactive method. According to the content of the method, a new grammatical topic is announced in the lesson, and the listener should explain it in different ways, i.e. draw different drawings on the board, show it with movements, compare it with the previous topic,

and engage the students in thinking with reinforcing questions. In phonetic training, short conversations in the audio text are listened to, and the text on the paper is filled in with the words written down, corresponding to the conversation in the audio text. The text given to the student and the conversation in the audio text are the same. Only when the text is carefully listened to and new phrases are memorized, the student can successfully fulfill the condition. Oral speech, knowledge and skills are formed through listening and understanding. Listening comprehension is closely related to the learning process. The listener remembers the words well and understands well when he listens. G.V. Rogova divides the content of teaching listening comprehension into three parts:

1. Linguistic part. This includes language and speech material.
2. Psychological part. This is the acquisition of skills and knowledge of listening and understanding voice speech.
3. Methodical part. Listening methods are taught to listeners, as well as the rules, principles, methods, and tools of listening comprehension technology.

While working on listening comprehension in the process of listening, the presence of texts about daily news, life, culture, and history of the people of the country whose language is being studied will increase the interest of the listeners. When the listener is trying to understand by listening, that is, when the listener listens to a speech with an unfamiliar content, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

1. Understanding some words, sentences, sentences (fragmenting comprehension).
2. Comprehension in details.
3. Superficial understanding of the main arguments (overall comprehension).
4. Critical comprehension.

When the broadcaster chooses a text for broadcasting, it is necessary to take into account the age, level of knowledge and experience of the listeners. For example, an unfamiliar text is selected. Unfamiliar words and phrases in the text are written on

the board with the title of the text. Questions and answers about the text can also be held. The process of teaching listening comprehension is carried out through the following steps: Activity:

1. Before listening. The title of the text and the questions are written on the board.

At the party:

(Amy Smith and Mike Thompson) 1. Where did Mike meet Amy?

2. When was last time they met?

3. What was his job then?

4. What does he do?

5. What is he studying at the moment? 2. While listening.

The conversation (dialogue) will be broadcast. Listeners find answers to the questions written on the board from the text. If necessary, the text can be repeated 1-2 times.

Answers:

1. They met at the party. 2. It was two years ago.

3. He was a pizza delivery man then.

4. He is a steward.

5. He is studying to be a pilot. After listening.

Listeners answer the questions. Words and phrases they do not understand are written on the board and the translation is explained. Listeners' answers are compared with each other's. Correct answers can be written on the board. It should also be said that during the study of the English language, home reading is also conducted. Studying at home is a fun and rich resource for unintentionally engaging students in the process of learning a foreign language on a variety of topics. Learners' knowledge and thinking skills will expand. Downloading original literature is done step by step. For example: exercises to the tune of "Jane Eyre" can be done:

I. Working in unfamiliar waters.

Words and phrases in tunes that are unfamiliar to the listeners are written on the board, and their pronunciation is explained to the listeners:

Lovable - ёкимтой. An orphan - етим.

To shake with fear (shook, shaken) - куркув билан кимирлатиш.

Without doubt - иккиланишсиз.

To earn one's living - яшаш учун пул топмок.

II. Questions and answers on the topic:

1. Why was Jane living with the Reed family?

2. Where did Jane go?

3. How did Jane live in Lowood?

4. Whom did she meet there?

5. Why do you think Jane didn't wish to be noticed by Mr. Rochester's guest? III.

Template burn exercises:

1. There I found a book ... pictures.

2. The two girls never played ... me.

3. Then one day I looked.....my window.

4. One dark night a week latter, I arrived ... Lowood.

IV. Make sentences by putting the words in place:

1. Explain, someday, I, shall, you, to.

2. Two, at, young, around, women, sat, table.

3. He, ask, did, to, marry, him, you.

4. Where, the, fire, Mr. Rochester, after, go, did.

In addition, students can be taught to write essays during homework. Once they are familiar with the essay topics, they can choose a topic of their choice and write an essay at home. For example:

1. The hero of the work you have written.

2. Describe the negative and positive images in the work.

3. Jane Eyre's childhood.

4. Your opinions about the main character of the work, etc. In this, lexical-grammatical difficulties arise. Encouraging students to express their opinions, the listener should also help to clarify the topic of the text. This process continues like this. At the end of the lesson, students who write correctly on the board are encouraged. It should be said that the student can properly divide the time during the lesson; consolidation of topics learned at the beginning of the lesson; use new methods in each lesson; it is advisable to use appropriate handouts for each lesson.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use of pedagogical technologies in the process of learning English will help students to improve their oral speech, listening comprehension, writing, reading skills and to communicate freely.

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